

Chemical Examination of the Bark of *Litsea consimilis*

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The chemical analysis of the bark oil of *Litsea consimilis* (Fam. Lauraceae), a medicinal plant growing wildy in Nainital district was reported earlier¹. An examination of the bark has further revealed the presence of β -amyrin and β -sitosterol.

Air-dried powdered bark (200 g.) was Soxhletted with petroleum (b.p. 60-80°). The light petroleum extract was concentrated and saponified with ethanolic potassium hydroxide in the usual manner. The unsaponifiable matter (6 g.) was separated and subjected to chromatography over Brockmann alumina (40 cm x 2 cm) using light petroleum, benzene, chloroform and their mixtures as eluents. Eluates were collected in fractions of 20-25 ml. each and evaporated to dryness (Table I).

TABLE I

Eluents	Fractions	Residue on evaporation
Petroleum (b. p. 60-80°)	1-8	Oily mass
Petroleum + benzene (3:2 v/v)	9-15	White solid
Petroleum + benzene (1:1 v/v)	16-26	Do
Benzene	27-32	Nil
Benzene + chloroform (3:2 v/v)	33-40	Shining flakes
Benzene + chloroform (1:1 v/v)	41-48	Do
Chloroform	49-54	Nil

Fractions (9-26) were crystallised from chloroform-methanol mixture (1 : 1) in needles (2.2 g.); m.p. 199-200°; $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 87^\circ.0$ (chloroform). (Found: C, 84.38; H, 11.85; Calc. for $C_{30}H_{50}O$: C, 84.51; H, 11.74%). The substance gave a positive Burchard-Liebermann reaction for a triterpene. It formed an acetate², m.p. 237-38°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 80^\circ.0$ (chloroform), which developed a yellow colour with tetranitromethane. (Found: C, 81.84; H, 11.24; Calc. for $C_{30}H_{50}O_2$: C, 82.06; H, 11.11%). Benzoste², m.p. 231-32°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 101.1^\circ$ (chloroform). (Found: C, 83.58; H, 10.30. Calc. for $C_{37}H_{54}O_2$: C, 83.77; H, 10.18%). a *p*-Nitrobenzoate², m.p. 257-58°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 95^\circ.6$ (chloroform). (Found: C, 76.84; H, 9.36; N, 2.51. Calc. for $C_{37}H_{53}NO_4$: C, 77.22; H, 9.22; N, 2.43%). The identity of the triterpene with β -amyrin was further confirmed by mixed m.p. and by a mixed chromatogram of the white solid with an authentic sample of β -amyrin.

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Fractions (33-48) on evaporation furnished a white solid with shining flakes which on repeated crystallisation from methanol-ethyl acetate mixture (1:1) yielded (2.7 g.) colorless flakes with constant m.p. 136-37°, [α]_D²⁵ -36°.5 (chloroform). (Found: C, 83.70; H, 12.12. Calc. for C₂₉H₅₀O: C, 84.05; H, 12.08%). The compound is fairly soluble in benzene, methanol and ethanol and readily soluble in chloroform, ethyl ether and ethyl acetate. The compound gave a positive Salkowski-Hesse reaction and developed a green colour in the Burchard-Liebermann test. It formed an acetate³, m.p. 126°, [α]_D²⁵ 42°. 0 (chloroform). (Found: C, 81.46; H, 11.51. Calc. for C₃₁H₅₂O₂: C, 81.57; H, 11.46%). Benzoate³, m.p. 144°, [α]_D²⁵ 14°.5 (chloroform). (Found: C, 83.18; H, 10.46. Calc. for C₃₆H₅₄O₂: C, 83.39; H, 10.42%). Digitonide⁴, m.p. 230°. (Found: C, 61.85; H, 8.61. Calc. for C₅₉H₉₀O. C₃₃H₅₀O₂₉: C, 61.91; H, 8.60%).

The identity of the compound with β -sitosterol was further established by mixed m.p. and by a mixed chromatogram of the compound with an authentic sample of β -sitosterol.

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